

57ASM – 192 | IFN γ -induced changes in mitochondrial metabolism as a novel strategy for pancreatic cancer therapy

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Introduction: Pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma (PDAC) is an aggressive disease for which there is currently no effective therapy. The PDAC tumours show repression of the anticancer immunity in their micro-environment. Immune checkpoint inhibitors aim to stimulate anticancer immune defence via activation of T-lymphocytes producing IFN γ , which was shown to induce cell death in malignant cells. Despite the well-established mechanism of IFN γ induced cell death, its effect on mitochondria and cellular metabolism remains elusive. Our goal was to study the role of IFN γ in regulation of mitochondrial biogenesis and its contribution to cell death.

Methods: Metabolic parameters were evaluated using flow-cytometry, confocal microscopy, and Oxygraph2k/Oroboros instrument. For in vivo studies, orthotopic and subcutaneously model of PDAC was engaged. Human and murine cell lines were grafted into NSG or C57BL/6 mice respectively. Treatment was applied by intraperitoneal injection.

Results: We show that IFN γ and IFN γ -producing immunotherapy represented by anti-PD-1 immune checkpoint inhibitor blocks aerobic glycolysis, prevents upregulation of glucose transporter and lactate secretion. Further, IFN γ regulates mitochondrial function in PDAC cells via increased autophagy of damaged mitochondria. These changes in metabolism make the pancreatic tumours more susceptible to OXPHOS inhibition by MitoTam, a potentially new anticancer agent that selectively targets highly polarized mitochondria of malignant cell, where induces electrochemical imbalance resulting in cell death. This combined therapy showed stabilization or rejection of tumours and significantly prolonged survival in all tested animals compared to immunotherapy or MitoTam alone.

Conclusion: IFN γ produced during immunotherapy regulates mitochondrial biogenesis in PDAC with metabolic shift to oxidative phosphorylation and improves tumour microenvironment. Our study therefore suggests a novel promising strategy for treatment of pancreatic cancer by simultaneous targeting of mitochondrial metabolism and immune checkpoints.

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57ASM – 200 | Mitochondrial morphology and metabolism in pancreatic β -cell form IF1 KO mice

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Introduction: Inhibitory factor 1 (IF1) is an endogenous regulator of ATP synthase. Previous studies have established that IF1 binds and inhibits ATP synthase upon a large decrease in membrane potential ($\Delta\Psi_m$) when ATP synthase reverses and hydrolyses ATP, preventing total ATP depletion. What is yet to be established is how IF1 regulates ATP synthesis under normal physiological conditions when the enzyme works in the regular forward mode. We have previously shown that IF1 regulates cellular respiration, ATP levels, and glucose-stimulated insulin secretion in model pancreatic β -cells (INS-1E) under normal physiological conditions 1, 2.

Aim: The aim of this study was to investigate cellular metabolism and mitochondrial morphology in pancreatic beta cells in-situ in pancreatic islets isolated from IF1 KO mice.

Material and Methods: We studied ATP levels in pancreatic islets treated with low and high glucose concentrations with inactive/active glucose-stimulated insulin secretion (GSIS). Insulin and glucagon expression was also studied by immunohistochemistry and compared between pancreatic islets of IF1 KO and WT mice. Moreover, using super-resolution microscopy, mitochondrial morphology was successfully visualized in pancreatic islets under different metabolic conditions.

Conclusion: Altogether, the obtained data provided further insight into the emerging role of IF1 in the metabolism of pancreatic beta cells. The project was funded by Grant Agency of the Czech Republic (No. GA22-02203S to Ing. Andrea Dlasková, Ph.D.).